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Needs Analysis for the Development of an AI-Based Medical English Teaching Program in Higher Education

Yüksek Öğretimde Yapay Zekâ Temelli Tıbbi Mesleki İngilizce Öğretim Programı Geliştirme Sürecine Yönelik Bir İhtiyaç Analizi Çalışması¹

ABSTRACT

The primary objective of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of an artificial intelligence-based Medical English for Specific Purposes (ESP) course within the context of higher education, and to conduct a comprehensive needs analysis by taking into account the perspectives of students, faculty members, and artificial intelligence-based applications. In the study, a convergent parallel design, one of the mixed methods designs that allows for the integrated interpretation of both qualitative and quantitative data, was adopted. The research was conducted within the Faculty of Medicine at a public university in Turkey, and data were collected through semi-structured interviews, a needs analysis survey, document analysis, and academic achievement records. The study group consisted of 204 medical students currently enrolled in the Faculty of Medicine and six faculty members with at least three years of professional teaching experience. The findings reveal that the existing Medical English for Specific Purposes curriculum does not sufficiently support students' fundamental linguistic skills such as professional communication, academic writing, listening, and speaking. Students reported particular deficiencies in areas such as terminology knowledge, case-based speaking practices, academic article analysis, and doctor-patient communication content. Faculty members, on the other hand, emphasized the necessity of updating the program's learning outcomes, strengthening the connection between course content and professional contexts, and moving beyond an exam-oriented approach by incorporating formative and process-based assessment strategies throughout the instructional period. Furthermore, the views of both students and faculty members underscored the need for effective integration of digital resources, simulation-based learning, and technologies such as augmented reality within the instructional process. Survey data indicate that students perceive themselves as having low proficiency particularly in clinical communication skills. Among the preferred instructional methods during the course were group work, role-playing, question-and-answer activities, and practice-based learning. Analyses conducted with the support of artificial intelligence also recommended that the program be supported by personalized learning pathways, verbal feedback systems, and speech recognition technologies. In conclusion, the findings highlight the necessity of designing a Medical English for Specific Purposes course that is compatible with the requirements of the contemporary era—interactive, personalized, and supported by educational technologies. In this context, the model proposed within the scope of the study offers original contributions at both theoretical and practical levels.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Program Development, Medical English, Needs Analysis

ÖZET

Bu araştırmanın temel amacı, yapay zekâ destekli bir Tıbbi Mesleki İngilizce dersinin yükseköğretim bağlamında ne derece etkili olabileceğini değerlendirmek ve bu kapsamda öğrencilerin, öğretim elemanlarının ve yapay zekâ tabanlı uygulamaların bakış açılarını dikkate alarak kapsamlı bir ihtiyaç analizi gerçekleştirmektir. Araştırmada, nitel ve nicel verilerin bir arada yorumlanmasına olanak sağlayan karma yöntem desenlerinden yakınsak paralel desen benimsenmiştir. Türkiye'deki bir devlet üniversitesinin Tıp Fakültesi bünyesinde yürütülen çalışmada, yapılandırılmış görüşmeler, ihtiyaç analizi anketi, doküman analizi ve akademik başarı kayıtları veri kaynakları olarak kullanılmıştır. Çalışma grubunu tıp fakültesinde öğrenim görmekte olan 204 öğrenci ile en az üç yıllık deneyime sahip 6 öğretim üyesi oluşturmaktadır. Elde edilen bulgular, mevcut Tıbbi Mesleki İngilizce öğretim programının öğrencilerin mesleki iletişim, akademik yazma, dinleme ve konuşma gibi temel dilsel becerilerini yeterince desteklemediğini ortaya koymaktadır. Öğrenciler, özellikle terminoloji bilgisi, vaka temelli konuşma uygulamaları, akademik makale analizi ve hasta-hekim diyaloglarına yönelik içeriklerde eksiklikler olduğunu belirtmişlerdir. Öğretim elemanları ise program çıktılarının güncellenmesi, ders içeriğinin mesleki bağlamlarla daha güçlü şekilde ilişkilendirilmesi ve ölçme-değerlendirme süreçlerinin sadece sınav temelli olmaktan çıkarılıp sürece yayılan uygulamalarla desteklenmesi gerektiğini ifade etmişlerdir. Ayrıca hem öğrenci hem öğretim elemanı görüşleri, öğretim sürecinde dijital kaynakların, simülasyon temelli öğrenmenin ve artırılmış gerçeklik gibi teknolojilerin etkin kullanımına duyulan ihtiyacı vurgulamıştır. Anket verileri, öğrencilerin özellikle klinik iletişim becerilerinde kendilerini düşük düzeyde yeterli gördüklerini göstermektedir. Katılımcıların ders sürecinde en çok tercih ettikleri yöntemlerin başında grup çalışması, rol oynama, soru-cevap etkinlikleri ve uygulama temelli öğrenme yer almaktadır. Yapay zekâ tabanlı analizler ise programın bireyselleştirilmiş öğrenme yolları, sözel geri bildirim sistemleri ve konuşma tanıma teknolojileriyle desteklenmesini önermektedir. Sonuç olarak, çağın gerekliliklerine uyumlu, etkileşimli, kişiselleştirilmiş ve teknoloji destekli bir Tıbbi Mesleki İngilizce öğretim programının tasarlanması gerekliliği ortaya konmuştur. Bu bağlamda çalışmada geliştirilen model önerisi hem kuramsal hem de uygulamalı düzeyde özgün katkılar sunmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Yapay Zekâ, Program Geliştirme, Tıbbi Mesleki İngilizce, İhtiyaç Analizi.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The intricate relationship between AI and education offers a promising future, where educators can harness AI to create enriched and effective learning experiences. As AI continues to shape educational environments, its integration into course design emerges as a tool with the potential to optimize teaching and learning processes and ultimately improve educational quality. In course planning, AI can play a critical role in personalizing learning experiences. By analyzing student data and behavior, AI can provide tailored content and assessments that enhance the overall effectiveness of instruction. Furthermore, AI can support the development of more engaging and targeted educational content by ensuring that learning materials align with students' interests and needs. Incorporating AI algorithms into course design can lead to the creation of more dynamic and adaptive learning environments that accommodate diverse learning styles and paces (Yu & Yu, 2023). From this perspective, as the role of AI in teaching and learning processes, and in the underlying design dimensions are examined more deeply, it is evident that AI holds significant potential to impact the field of Curriculum and Instruction.

As emphasized in the literature, AI's ability to personalize learning experiences for students is considered highly advantageous in course design (Zhao & Nazir, 2022). To fully harness the potential of AI and to gain a comprehensive understanding of its strengths and limitations within program development processes, further research is needed to evaluate its impact on educational programs and the role of educators in effectively utilizing these technologies. Such studies will provide critical insights into the most effective and ethical ways to integrate AI into educational settings, enabling educators to enhance the learning experience while maintaining their vital role in students' academic and personal development. Hence, AI is increasingly regarded as a transformative tool in education, capable of delivering personalized learning experiences, enhancing teaching and learning processes, and improving instructional design (Elbawab & Henriques, 2023). Moreover, it is suggested that AI's potential in education extends beyond efficiency and personalized learning (Marino et al., 2023). As AI-based educational solutions continue to evolve, efforts to bridge critical gaps in the teaching and learning process appear increasingly promising. By integrating AI tools with human intelligence, it is feasible to develop advanced intelligent educational systems, tools, and platforms that cater to diverse learning styles and needs (Huh, 2023). The synergy between teacher input and AI appears poised to revolutionize the educational landscape by delivering a stable and high-quality learning experience that combines the best of both worlds. In conclusion, as educators continue to explore AI's potential, emphasis on maintaining a human-centered approach and leveraging AI to support—rather than replace—the role of the educator will be crucial in ensuring a holistic and effective educational experience for students (Harry, 2023).

Current research forecasts that AI technologies have the potential to shape the future of education in alignment with digital transformation (Hinojo-Lucena et al., 2019; Chounta et al., 2021). Supporting this projection, one of the limited studies on the subject by Popenici and Kerr (2017) examined the impact of AI on teaching and learning processes in higher education. Their findings revealed that the development of technological pedagogical knowledge should evolve in parallel with digital transformations to maximize AI's potential to improve educational experiences. In addition, Alkanaa (2022) conducted a study focusing on preservice teachers' awareness of AI's potential impacts in science education. The results demonstrated that high awareness of AI technologies among students positively influenced the teaching and learning processes. Based on this body of knowledge, and to ensure that educational programs and processes do not lag behind the requirements of the digital age, this study aims to conduct a needs analysis to examine the effectiveness of an AI-based Medical English course in higher education. In line with this primary objective, the following sub-questions will be addressed:

1. What are the needs of medical students regarding Medical English?
2. What are the opinions of medical students regarding the Medical English course?
3. What are the opinions of medical faculty members regarding the Medical English course?
4. What are the needs of medical students regarding the Medical English course as identified through the needs analysis survey?
5. What are the opinions of artificial intelligence regarding the Medical English course?

2. METHOD

2.1. Research Design

In this study, which conducted a needs analysis of an AI-based Medical English course designed at the Faculty of Medicine of a public university in Turkey, a mixed methods research design was employed due to the integration of both quantitative and qualitative data for comprehensive interpretation. The mixed methods approach is defined as a methodology that combines qualitative and quantitative approaches within a single study (Johnson & Christensen, 2008). In other words, it entails the integration of both qualitative and quantitative data and methodologies within the same research framework (Gay, Mills, & Airasian, 2009). In this study, the convergent parallel mixed design, a subtype of mixed methods research, was adopted. In identifying the needs of medical students regarding the Medical English course, the discrepancy model, one of the widely used approaches to needs assessment, was utilized. In this stage, based on the discrepancy between expected and observed performance (Stufflebeam et al., 1985), semi-structured interviews were conducted with medical students to explore how their previous learning experiences related to the Medical English course had occurred, and to determine how the instructional process could be more effectively designed. These interviews provided insights into their expectations from the course and their prior learning experiences. Additionally, semi-structured interviews were conducted with faculty members in the Faculty of Medicine to gather their perspectives on the course, particularly regarding its relevance to medical practice and its potential for transfer into professional life. In alignment with the primary objective of this study, AI-based tools were also consulted during the analysis phase to support the interpretation of findings. Moreover, a comprehensive review of the related literature was conducted, and a Needs Analysis Survey on Medical English was developed. This instrument included multiple-response items and an open-ended question to assess how competent students perceive themselves in Medical English, which teaching methods and techniques they prefer, and what kinds of assessment tools they would favor in addition to midterm and final exams. Finally, to ensure that the instructional program to be developed would be aligned with student needs, a document analysis was also carried out.

2.2. Research Group

In this section, where the needs analysis of the study was conducted, purposeful sampling was employed, as it allows the researcher to select participants who meet specific criteria in line with the purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). Specifically, criterion sampling, a subtype of purposeful sampling, was used to ensure relevance and depth of data. Accordingly, the semi-structured interviews were conducted with a total of 12 participants, including 6 medical students and 6 faculty members who teach them.

The faculty participants were selected based on the following criteria: (1) having taken Medical English courses at the undergraduate level, (2) having at least three years of teaching experience in a medical faculty (to ensure relevant professional insight), and (3) voluntary participation in the study. As for the student participants, the selection criteria included: (1) being in the 4th, 5th, or internship year of medical education, (2) having completed Medical English I, II, and III courses, and (3) willingness to participate in the study voluntarily. Regarding the implementation of the needs analysis survey, the same selection criteria were applied, and a total of 204 medical students were reached and included in the survey.

2.3. Data Collection Instruments and Procedures

To identify the needs of medical students regarding the Medical English course in the Faculty of Medicine, two main instruments were employed: semi-structured interview forms and the “Needs Analysis Survey for the Medical English Course.”

2.3.1. Semi-Structured Interview Forms for Medical Students and Faculty Members

Interviews are commonly used to explore participants' experiences, emotions, and behaviors that cannot be directly observed (Merriam, 2009). At this stage of the research, semi-structured interview forms consisting of open-ended questions were developed by the researcher, taking into account the purpose of the study and relevant literature. Care was taken to ensure that the interview questions were conversational in tone, aligned with everyday language, easily comprehensible, focused on a single idea, open-ended, and concise (Krueger & Casey, 2015).

The prepared interview forms were subjected to expert review, and a pilot implementation was conducted with two participants, one student and one faculty member, to assess clarity and comprehensibility. Revisions were made based on expert feedback, and the final versions of the interview forms were completed. Face-to-face, one-on-one interviews were conducted. Each interview lasted approximately 45

minutes, and the data collection process was completed within 15 days. With the consent of the participants, all interviews were audio-recorded for data accuracy.

2.3.2. Needs Analysis Survey for the Medical English Course

In order to determine both the perceived proficiency levels of medical students who had previously taken the Medical English course and their related needs, the researcher developed a Needs Analysis Survey. The survey consisted of a total of 11 items: the first 8 were rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = not proficient at all, 5 = highly proficient), items 9 and 10 were multiple-response questions, and item 11 was open-ended.

Since the discrepancy model of needs assessment was adopted for this study—focusing on the gap between expected and observed performance (Stufflebeam et al., 1985)—a document analysis was initially conducted to inform the development of the survey. In this context, the first 8 items were derived from the target proficiency outcomes expected from students in the existing Medical English curriculum. The remaining items addressed the instructional methods and techniques preferred by students, as well as alternative assessment tools beyond midterm and final exams. Additionally, the final open-ended question aimed to gather information about students' prior learning experiences related to the course and to collect suggestions for improving the curriculum development process.

The initial draft of the survey was evaluated for content and face validity by two instructors working at the School of Foreign Languages who had prior experience teaching Medical English. Revisions were made based on their expert feedback. The revised version of the survey was piloted with six students to assess the clarity and interpretability of the items, and no issues were identified.

Subsequently, in order to ensure the validity and reliability of the instrument, a pilot study was conducted. A pilot test is crucial for identifying potential issues in a draft instrument and must be conducted with a group sharing similar characteristics with the target population to ensure the accuracy and generalizability of the results (Büyükoztürk et al., 2019). In this regard, the finalized version of the survey was administered to 200 fifth- and sixth-year medical students. To assess the instrument's reliability, a test-retest method was applied by re-administering the survey to the same group three weeks later, and the correlation between the two sets of results was examined. Based on expert opinions and the results of the reliability analysis, no issues were identified regarding the overall reliability of the instrument, and the survey was deemed ready for implementation.

2.4. Data Analysis

The quantitative data obtained from the study were analyzed using the SPSS statistical software package. Initially, the data were tested to determine whether the assumptions of normality were met. Parametric tests were used when the normality assumption was satisfied; otherwise, non-parametric tests were applied. The significance level for all statistical analyses was set at $p < .05$. The qualitative data analysis was conducted based on Saldaña's (2019) perspective, without the use of computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software (CAQDAS). The analysis followed an inductive process, progressing from code to categories and ultimately to themes, using the content analysis method to identify patterns and similarities within the data (Strauss & Corbin, 1990).

2.5. Validity and Reliability of the Study

Ensuring the validity and reliability of a study is of critical importance for producing accurate and high-quality results (Büyükoztürk et al., 2018). Throughout all stages of the research process, expert opinions were consulted, and decisions were made in continuous interaction with field specialists. In addition, a triangulation strategy was employed to approach and evaluate the research topic from multiple perspectives. To enhance data richness and ensure methodological rigor, multiple data collection instruments were utilized, including an academic achievement test, a self-efficacy scale related to English, an attitude scale toward vocational foreign language courses, and semi-structured classroom observations. The experimental and control groups were determined through random assignment, and following the data collection process, the demographic information of the participants was kept confidential with a clear statement that such information would not be shared with third parties. At the beginning of the study, participants in the study group were required to sign an informed consent form, and ethical approval was obtained from the relevant ethics committee for the conduct of the research.

3. FINDINGS

The first research question addressed within the scope of this study is: “What are the needs of medical faculty students regarding the Medical English course?” In order to answer this question, a comprehensive needs analysis was conducted. As part of this process, individual interviews were held with both medical faculty students and instructors. Additionally, a survey was administered to measure students’ perceived proficiency in Medical English. Furthermore, students’ past academic records were analyzed to gain insights into their achievement levels. Document analysis was also employed during the needs analysis stage. In this context, a review of the relevant literature was conducted, including international examples, and the existing Medical English curriculum was examined. Expert opinions were also sought. Accordingly, the findings obtained from the needs analysis process are presented under thematic headings.

3.1. Findings from Interviews Conducted with Medical Faculty Students

In order to identify the needs of medical faculty students regarding the Medical English course, semi-structured interviews were conducted with six fifth-year medical students. The responses provided by the participants to the interview questions were analyzed, and the resulting findings and main themes are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Theme and Category List Based on Medical Students’ Opinions

Theme	Category
Content related needs	Terminology Knowledge
	Clinical Communication Skills
	Academic Reading and Writing Skills
Teaching learning process-related needs	Applied Instruction
	Variety in Teaching Methods
	Variety in Instructional Materials
Assessment-related needs	Process Evaluation
	Alternative Assessment Tools

An examination of Table 1 reveals that the data gathered from the students' perspectives can be categorized under three primary themes. The first of these is the theme of Content-Related Needs. This theme emerged from students' emphasis on the significance of terminology knowledge and the competencies expected to be developed through the course, both in their academic training and future professional practice. Furthermore, student reflections highlighting the importance of communication skills required in real-life patient interactions led to the inclusion of clinical communication skills as a subcategory under this theme.

Analysis of the students’ responses reveals that medical terminology knowledge was frequently emphasized as a major content need. For example, Student 2 stated, “*Most of the material we encounter is in English, and because many of the words are highly technical, it’s even difficult to find them in dictionaries. After taking this course, I started to understand the terminology in my other classes better.*” Similarly, Student 1 noted, “*We tend to translate English words based on their most common meaning, but in professional medical English, the term often carries an entirely different definition. The important thing is the medical meaning.*”

Students expressed the view that terminology knowledge is essential not only during their medical education but also in clinical settings, and therefore, they believed that the course content should not be limited to vocabulary but also incorporate relevant grammar structures. For instance:

“Knowing only terms and abbreviations is not enough. Yes, we definitely need to know those, but if we don’t understand how to use them in a sentence—like which verb to pair with a term or where it fits grammatically—we get stuck.” (Student 6)

“Even if I understand medical terms when doing listening or speaking exercises, if I don’t know the grammar, I feel like all the vocabulary I’ve learned is wasted. Sometimes I know every word in a sentence, but I still can’t fully understand it. That’s because we’re missing the basics. We should’ve improved our English before this course, but I think it should still be included within this course for better results.” (Student 3)

These statements suggest that terminology knowledge should be considered a key component under content-related needs. In addition, many students emphasized the need to enhance their clinical communication skills, particularly through real-life hospital dialogues, listening activities, and authentic scenarios, which they believed would help them transfer what they learn into their professional practice.

Students agreed on the importance of learning both the meaning and pronunciation of medical terms. They also highlighted the necessity of practicing speaking and listening skills in clinical contexts:

“Not everyone in our country speaks Turkish. If a foreign patient comes, we need to communicate clearly. This isn’t something to take lightly—it’s about health. So we need to learn not only the meaning but also the correct pronunciation of medical terms. The listening dialogues in class are helpful. At first, we couldn’t understand anything, but now we’re doing better. More speaking practice would help a lot.” (Student 1)

“There are international conferences, and we need to attend them to stay up to date on diseases and treatments. Tourist-level English isn’t enough. We have to understand and speak in a medical context. These things should be included in the course.” (Student 4)

“To become a qualified doctor, we need to focus on communication skills while we’re still in school. That includes communication with patients, fellow doctors, nurses, pharmacists, and hospital staff. When you’re in a hospital setting, you realize how important this is. Pronunciation, comprehension, and speaking are all key—and not just using English but actual medical terminology.” (Student 2)

“Let me give a simple example. During my hospital internship, a foreigner asked me, ‘Where is ER?’ I actually knew that ER means emergency room, but I didn’t understand it when it was spoken aloud. I had learned the term, but because we never focused on pronunciation in class, I couldn’t even show the patient where the emergency room was.” (Student 5)

These insights suggest that medical terminology and language skills used in clinical communication are closely interconnected needs. Students indicated difficulties and a lack of confidence in using the correct terminology during patient interactions or in professional English-speaking environments. As Student 4 remarked, *“Medical English is not like everyday English—it’s harder. The moment I realize I’m using the wrong terms while speaking, my confidence drops.”*

Another area emphasized by the participant students under the theme of content-related needs was the development of academic reading and writing skills. Based on the students’ statements indicating difficulties in understanding and analyzing academic articles in English, it can be inferred that this skill set is a critical requirement both in the educational process and in their future professional careers. The findings reveal a consensus that mastering academic language is essential for accessing up-to-date medical information and developments, contributing to the field scientifically, and participating actively in the international health community. The students expressed the following opinions in this regard:

“To keep up with current medical developments, we must understand Medical English. But knowing only the terms is not enough; we should be able to read, and even write, academic papers. This is especially essential for medical conferences.” (Student 1)

“There are constant developments and changes in our field, as in every field. New treatments, diseases, etc. For example, during the COVID period, to follow the latest developments or read the articles written by experts, we must be proficient in professional language.” (Student 4)

“There are databases like PubMed and Medline, and they are in English. Even just to conduct a keyword search or to review the literature, we need Medical English. And when we don’t understand what we read, we lose a lot of time trying to make sense of it.” (Student 6)

In addition to the above, Student 2 and Student 5 also emphasized the necessity of becoming proficient in academic reading and writing to present case studies or attend international conferences and academic meetings. Furthermore, the importance of academic reading and writing skills was underlined for understanding textbooks, reports used worldwide, global databases, and academic publications in international journals. One student expressed the following:

“There are lots of global clinical medicine books and protocols. We need Medical English to be able to read and understand them. For example, the World Health Organization reports... Of course, there are translations, but when we have the chance to read the original, I believe the training we receive should not go to waste.” (Student 4)

Another subtheme under content-related needs was the necessity for Medical English proficiency tailored to foreign language exams. Depending on the countries where they wish to work and their career goals,

medical students are often required to take various standardized language exams. Student 5 and Student 6 stated:

“We need to pass foreign language exams to get our specialization.” (Student 5)

“To apply for international programs or to work abroad, we need to succeed in these recognized exams. Since we cover such topics in this course, I find it important.” (Student 6)

Thus, it is evident that academic reading and writing skills should be considered an integral component of the course content, especially in relation to standardized foreign language proficiency assessments.

Another theme that emerged from the analysis of student feedback pertains to the learning-teaching process. Within this theme, the first prominent category is “practice-based instruction.” Students believe that the terminology knowledge, clinical communication skills, and academic reading and writing skills acquired in this course should be reinforced through practical activities such as role-playing, simulations, and case analyses. Several students pointed out that the lack of practical applications limits their opportunity to apply what they have learned. Their statements include:

“We learn the medical English terms, but we don’t get much chance to practice them. It would be better if we used what we learned.” (Student 1)

“I would love to practice scenarios or patient communication. These types of activities should definitely be included in the course.” (Student 5)

Based on these comments, it can be suggested that integrating practical components into the course would enhance its effectiveness. These views highlight the students’ needs related to practical preparation for their future professional lives.

Additionally, students emphasized the need for diverse teaching methods during the instructional process. Complementing the need for applied instruction, the use of interactive methods was seen as beneficial for reinforcing learned knowledge. The following remarks reflect this:

“Some students think individual work is better, while others like me find group work more effective. If we used both in class, it could be more productive for everyone.” (Student 2)

“For instance, we could do drama-style activities related to patient communication—like the listening dialogues we hear, but we could write and act them out ourselves. Though some students are passive in group activities, alternative activities could be arranged for them too. It would be a win-win.” (Student 5)

“I love the question-answer activities we do in class. It’s like a brainstorming session. If we had more of those, we’d participate more actively, and the process would be more efficient.” (Student 6)

These responses suggest that the diversity of teaching methods contributes to students’ active engagement, enables the application of learned skills, and ensures that both individual and group learning styles are addressed effectively.

Another identified category under the learning-teaching process theme was the need for diverse materials. Students reported a lack of visual materials and expressed a need for more current and interactive resources. The following statements illustrate this:

“Learning vocabulary is more effective with pictures, videos, and photos. Using these while covering any topic would be really helpful. I wish we had more of them in our lessons.” (Student 2)

“Video-based resources could have been used. I think they’re more memorable.” (Student 3)

“Relying solely on textbooks can be boring. We need more when learning a language. Digital resources, e-books, applications, etc. Learning through videos is also enjoyable. It involves listening and, if we talk about what we watched, speaking too. It would be better for us that way.” (Student 6)

Apart from learning-teaching needs, the analysis also identified two categories related to assessment and evaluation. In regard to Medical English terminology—highlighted under content needs—it was observed that students do not feel the need to study consistently during the semester due to a lack of assignments being graded outside midterm and final exams. This indicates a lack of continuous engagement. Students

stressed the importance of being assessed throughout the semester to remain actively involved. Student 3 explained:

"I take notes and feel like I learn during the exercises, but later I forget most of the terms. Especially topics like specific diseases or treatments... Even if I know the meaning of a word, the medical meaning is often something entirely different. If you don't repeat it, you forget. Medical terms are hard to remember anyway—too many abbreviations, and their meanings change in context. It's hard. We have some assignments other than exams, but the instructor says they won't be graded, just learn without stress. So most people don't take them seriously. As a result, by the next week, I forget the medical terms." (Student 3)

"Although we do exercises in class, we only prepare for the midterm and final exams. Apart from that, our other courses are already intense, so we don't really study for this one. But if we had assignments where we could get feedback, we'd see our mistakes and reinforce the learning. Honestly, we just aim to pass. Our schedule is tight. But this course is also very important for our future. So cramming before exams doesn't really help much." (Student 5)

As these reflections suggest, students feel a need for formative assessment. Incorporating feedback-supported applied activities and interim evaluations into the process would likely enhance learning outcomes. Moreover, some student responses also pointed to a need for alternative assessment tools. Existing midterm and final exams are perceived as overly focused on theoretical knowledge and insufficient in evaluating communication skills. Examples of such opinions include:

"Our exams are structured as board exams. However, there are no exams assessing speaking, writing, or listening skills. Okay, now that I think about it, it would definitely be more difficult if there were. But at least we would actually learn." (Student 1)

"Including myself, I observed that most of my classmates participate in class; we do well in listening activities and other tasks. But we may not perform as well in the exam. Our exam week is extremely intense. We can even forget what we've learned. If what we do in class were also taken into account in the assessment... Or there are some technological tools—like Kahoot!, for example. If we used those and got some points even if not included in the main exam, it would still help. Writing and acting out dialogues would also be useful. I think everyone would participate more, and we'd also be evaluated through different methods." (Student 2)

Based on these statements, it can be inferred that due to various external factors, students may not always be able to demonstrate their performance adequately during formal exams. Therefore, the use of alternative assessment tools throughout the learning process would be beneficial. The findings suggest that, in addition to the current exam system, incorporating formative and performance-based assessments into the process could support the development of the skills that students actually need. Furthermore, the necessity of improving the assessment and evaluation methods is directly linked to enhancing both the content and instructional processes of the course, thereby allowing a more effective response to students' evolving needs.

3.2. Findings from Interviews Conducted with Faculty Members of the Medical School

In order to identify the specific needs of medical students regarding the Medical English course, semi-structured interviews were conducted with six faculty members currently teaching at the Faculty of Medicine. The main themes and findings derived from their responses to the interview questions are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Theme and Category List Based on Faculty Members' Opinions

Theme	Category
Needs Related to Professional Development	Clinical Language Development
	Academic Language Development
Needs Related to the Program	Updating Learning Outcomes
	Revising Instructional Components
	Improving Assessment and Evaluation

Faculty members were asked to reflect on their own experiences with Medical English during their student years. Most reported that they had insufficient training in this area. These personal experiences allowed the faculty to identify current gaps in the curriculum and suggest improvements for students' professional development. Emphasis was placed on the importance of medical English for clinical practice, particularly

with regard to communication with patients and mastery of medical terminology. Sample participant statements on this issue include:

“Our medical English courses were largely theoretical. Basic medical terminology was taught, but there was no content aimed at developing practical communication or spoken English skills. This caused difficulties for me in international patient communication and when presenting at conferences. I wish we had received more interactive training.” (Faculty Member 4)

“Our students need to focus on patient communication and case scenarios. They will face challenges in these areas in the future—just as we did. They can now work on these skills through practical classwork.” (Faculty Member 5)

“If they want to succeed in their careers and on international platforms, they need to develop patient communication skills. Understanding medical histories, explaining procedures, and creating treatment plans are essential. This isn’t everyday spoken language; it requires technical vocabulary. Students are very lacking in this regard.” (Faculty Member 6)

In light of these views, it is evident that medical English instruction should address clinical communication skills and appropriate use of terminology. Another need identified by faculty members is the development of students’ academic language skills. Students must be able to read and write academic literature, participate in international conferences, and strengthen their research competencies. Statements related to this theme include:

“Physicians must stay current. I need language skills to follow medical literature and read global academic studies. So do my students, who are future doctors.” (Faculty Member 1)

“I believe this course should focus on addressing gaps in academic English and terminology for young medical professionals.” (Faculty Member 3)

“We collaborate on international projects. Language skills are vital. Academic meetings, scientific presentations, discussions... all require confidence in the language. Students still struggle even with literature reviews. They lack reading comprehension and analytical skills.” (Faculty Member 5)

“Students’ comprehension of articles varies. They struggle with terms and grammar when writing case reports. They also have difficulty following English-language seminars. These skills must be developed.” (Faculty Member 6)

These insights underscore the need for the Medical English course to improve students’ academic language performance, including reading and writing medical content, mastering terminology, and developing listening and speaking skills in academic contexts.

The second major theme identified through interviews was "Needs Related to the Program." This theme included three categories: updating learning outcomes, revising instructional practices, and improving assessment. Faculty agreed that current course objectives are largely theoretical and should be updated to include practical skills. Suggestions aligned with previously identified needs in communication, terminology usage, and academic literacy. Example statements:

“Students learn theory, but applying it in real life is the real skill—like presenting a case, conducting an English interview with a patient, or explaining a treatment plan. Grammar and vocabulary aren’t enough. The outcomes should reflect real clinical needs.” (Faculty Member 1)

“Terminology is important—it’s the foundation. But what really matters is how to use it. Students must develop all four language skills—speaking, listening, reading, writing—in a functional way. The program should reflect modern professional needs.” (Faculty Member 2)

“In the health sector, English is essential. Medical professionals need it to communicate with foreign patients, explain treatments, or give presentations. Practical skills must be included in the outcomes.” (Faculty Member 4)

“I believe the outcomes should support both academic and professional goals. That means equipping students with professional-level language skills.” (Faculty Member 5)

Faculty consensus indicated the need to revise learning outcomes to enhance the course's effectiveness. In addition, the instructional practices themselves were seen as needing modernization. Faculty recommended using up-to-date materials, integrating interactive activities, and balancing theoretical and practical learning:

"We need more interactive, practice-based activities. Problem-solving should be a key component." (Faculty Member 2)

"Effective methods should be used to engage students—particularly those aligned with real-life clinical scenarios. This helps them apply the vocabulary and structures they learn." (Faculty Member 3)

"Students need to be engaged. They're already overwhelmed with other courses. If they become active in your course and enjoy it, their attitudes toward English will improve. Activities like discussions, group speaking tasks, and the use of foreign sources will boost their motivation." (Faculty Member 5)

"We must incorporate technology. Everything is digital now. Students talk about apps—they use them, and I use them too. Using these tools in class is enjoyable and educational. In my experience, they work." (Faculty Member 6)

These insights suggest that updating instructional methods will improve the quality of Medical English education. Real-world scenarios and needs-based content should be integrated to ensure student engagement. Practical methods such as role-play, case scenarios, simulations, and interactive group activities were consistently recommended.

Faculty members also identified the improvement of assessment methods as a key program need. They stressed that current evaluations focus too much on theory and fail to assess real-life language use. Recommendations included simulation-based evaluations, oral exams, and continuous assessment practices:

"The current evaluation system is overly theoretical. It doesn't measure students' real-life communication or application skills. We need to add simulations, oral exams, and case-based assessments to get a better picture of their competence." (Faculty Member 1)

"Written exams only test memorization. But we want to know how students use English in communication and case presentations. More performance-based tools are needed—like simulated patient interviews or written case reports." (Faculty Member 2)

"We lack continuous assessment. Students should not be evaluated solely at the end of term. Weekly quizzes, feedback, and small group projects would let us track progress more effectively." (Faculty Member 5)

"It's important to provide feedback during the learning process. After analyzing an article or solving a case, we should show students where they need to improve. That way, assessment becomes a learning tool." (Faculty Member 6)

According to these findings, assessment in Medical English courses should go beyond theoretical knowledge and focus on students' ability to apply their skills in professional contexts. The current system's emphasis on memorization is inadequate for evaluating practical competencies. Faculty emphasized the importance of performance-based and process-oriented assessment, the use of standardized criteria, and integration of digital tools.

3.3. Findings of the Needs Analysis Survey on the Medical English Course

The table below presents the results of the survey conducted with medical students regarding their self-perceived proficiency levels in various aspects of Medical English. Students rated their competencies on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from (1) Not at all proficient to (5) Highly proficient. Additionally, students were asked to indicate their preferred instructional methods and assessment techniques for the Medical English course.

Table 3. Findings of the Needs Analysis Survey

	%					Mode	Median
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)		
	Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Proficient	Highly		
1. Knowledge of medical English terminology	20.4	13.9	10	49.8	6	4	4
2. Understanding medical texts written in English	16.4	10.4	30.3	35.3	7.5	4	3
3. Understanding medical terms heard during conversations	50.7	30.8	12.9	4.5	1.0	1	1
4. Effectively using medical English terms in conversation	33.8	45.8	16.4	2.0	1.0	2	2
5. Using medical English in clinical communication	24.4	56.2	16.4	2.0	1.0	2	2
6. Writing English case reports in medical context	69.7	19.4	8.5	1.5	1.0	1	1
7. Understanding medical English in language exams for medical specialization	15.9	44.8	29.4	8.0	2.0	2	2
8. Using medical English for reviewing the medical literature	16.4	16.4	11.4	48.8	7	4	4
9. Which teaching methods would you prefer to be used in the Medical English course?						N	%
	Individual work					134	15.3
	Group work					140	16
	Role-play / drama					145	16.6
	Question-and-answer activities					147	16.8
	Discussion sessions					0	0
	Project-based activities (e.g., preparing patient reports)					102	11.7
	Video-based learning (e.g., watching medical procedure videos)					103	11.8
	Making a presentation					0	0
	Online platforms and applications (e.g., Quizlet, Kahoot)					103	11.8
10. Apart from midterm and final exams, which of the following assessment and evaluation methods would you prefer to be used for measuring your success in the Medical English course?						N	%
	Short quizzes during the term					11	1.3
	Assignments					54	6.2
	Oral exams					34	3.9
	Performance-based assessment					99	11.3
	Evaluation of classroom activities and outputs					115	13.2
	Participation					151	17.3
	Attendance					151	17.3
	Self-assessment					130	14.9
	Peer-assessment					129	14.8

An examination of the percentage values in Table 6 reveals that students consider themselves “proficient” only in items 1, 2, and 8. For items 4, 5, and 7, they rate themselves as “slightly proficient,” while for items 3 and 6, the majority report being “not at all proficient.” Additionally, very few students perceive themselves as “highly proficient” in any item.

Specifically, 49.8% of the participants indicated they were proficient in “medical English terminology knowledge,” while only 6% rated themselves as highly proficient in this area. Regarding “understanding a medical text written in English,” 35.3% rated themselves as proficient and 7.5% as highly proficient. For “using medical English expressions necessary for reviewing the medical literature,” 48.8% reported being proficient and 7% highly proficient.

On the other hand, the combined percentages of those who reported being not at all or slightly proficient show that 81.5% struggle with “understanding medical English terms heard in conversation”; 79.6% with “effectively using medical English terms during speech”; 80.6% with “using medical English in clinical communication”; 89.1% with “writing English case reports in medical contexts”; and 60.7% with “understanding medical English expressions in specialty exams.”

Additionally, students were asked which instructional methods and techniques they would prefer in the Medical English course. Responses indicate that question-and-answer activities (16.8%), role-play/drama (16.6%), group work (16%), and individual work (15.3%) were the most preferred options.

In the final question of the survey, students were asked which assessment methods, apart from midterm and final exams, they would prefer to be used for evaluating their success in the course. The most frequently chosen methods were class participation (17.3%), class attendance (17.3%), self-assessment (14.9%), and peer assessment (14.8%).

3.4. Opinions of Artificial Intelligence on the Needs in Medical English Courses

As part of the needs analysis for the development of the Medical English curriculum, the perspectives of the artificial intelligence tool ChatGPT were also consulted. Below is a synthesis of its analysis and proposed needs, taking into account both current educational trends and communication demands in the medical field.

Language and Communication-Oriented Needs:

1. Medical Terminology Knowledge

- a. Students need to learn core medical terms and their contextual usage.
- b. Understanding the differences between Latin-origin terms and their English equivalents.

2. Doctor-Patient Communication

- a. Developing the ability to show empathy and convey medical information in plain language.
- b. Acquiring skills in questioning, explaining, and taking patient histories.

3. Professional Presentations and Speaking

- a. Developing the ability to present medical cases in English at international conferences or team meetings.
- b. Using professional language fluently and effectively.

4. Cultural Awareness and Ethical Communication

- a. Communicating respectfully and sensitively with patients and colleagues from diverse cultural backgrounds.

Academic and Technical Needs:

1. Reading Medical Literature

- a. Quickly and accurately reading and understanding medical articles in English.
- b. Analyzing and synthesizing findings from scientific research.

2. Academic Writing

- a. Writing academic articles, case reports, and patient records in English.
- b. Using accurate sentence structures and developing a professional academic writing style.

3. Conducting Research and Data Analysis

- a. Finding reliable English sources and reporting relevant data.
- b. Presenting research findings in English effectively.

Practical and Technology-Supported Needs:

1. Simulation-Based Applications

- a. Practicing communication with AI-supported tools simulating real patients.
- b. Engaging in case-based learning to solve clinical scenarios.

2. Translation Skills

- a. Accurately translating Turkish medical terms and concepts into English.

3. Pronunciation and Fluency

- a. Practicing correct pronunciation with AI-powered speech analysis tools.
- b. Enhancing listening and comprehension skills through medical podcasts and videos.

Career-Oriented Needs:

1. International Collaboration

- a. Acquiring language skills for participation in global medical conferences or international education/internship programs.
 - b. Preparing a professional CV and conducting mock interviews for job applications.
2. Professional English Certifications
- a. Preparing for standardized exams such as the Medical Specialty Exam (TUS) that include English proficiency components.
3. Multidisciplinary Communication
- a. Developing communication skills to collaborate with doctors, nurses, and other healthcare professionals from different specialties.

Assessment and Feedback Needs:

1. Personalized Learning
- a. Creating individualized learning plans targeting each student's weaknesses.
 - b. Using AI-supported assessment tools to provide ongoing feedback.
2. Performance-Based Evaluation
- a. Evaluating acquired skills through clinical scenarios, group work, and role-play activities.

These AI-identified needs are essential for medical students to succeed both in their careers and in everyday professional practice.

4. CONCLUSION and RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of the needs analysis reveal that the current curriculum of the Medical English for Specific Purposes course does not adequately address the linguistic and professional needs of the students. In particular, the existing learning outcomes fail to sufficiently encompass the specific skills required in clinical practice, such as communicating with patients in English, producing academic texts, and comprehending international medical literature. This indicates that outcomes primarily focused on theoretical knowledge fall short in preparing students for real-world tasks. In alignment with the perspectives of scholars such as Harden (2001) and Richards (2001), it is essential that language learning outcomes be context-specific, actionable, and student-centered. Therefore, revising the program outcomes to include tangible objectives—such as clinical communication, academic writing, and interdisciplinary literacy—has become imperative.

From a content perspective, significant deficiencies in medical terminology knowledge were identified. Students appear to struggle with recognizing, contextualizing, and accurately using frequently encountered medical terms. Accordingly, the content structure of the course must be redesigned around foundational medical terminology. The implementation of concept maps, collaborative and individual study, and context-based question-and-answer activities is recommended to reinforce this knowledge. Moreover, the findings underscore the need to integrate components that support the development of clinical communication skills. Authentic learning strategies such as drama, role-play, and case-based scenarios should be embedded into the curriculum. Drawing from Dewey's (1938) principle that "learning begins with experience," it becomes evident that learning environments should mirror real-life practices.

Additionally, academic reading and writing skills have emerged as a critical area of concern frequently mentioned by students. The current curriculum does not sufficiently represent these competencies. Therefore, structured writing activities—focusing on medical article analysis, scientific reporting, and scholarly debate—should be incorporated. Furthermore, encouraging both individual and collaborative writing practices, along with the use of peer review mechanisms, will contribute to internalizing academic writing norms and enhancing critical thinking.

Students also reported challenges in both comprehending and actively using medical English terms during listening and speaking activities. To address this, the curriculum should integrate patient-doctor dialogues, medical podcasts, and interactive listening exercises. For speaking skill development, case-based dialogues, spontaneous speech tasks, word games, and group discussions centered on clinical scenarios are recommended. Such activities will strengthen oral communication and contribute to students' professional linguistic identity. In line with Vygotsky's (1978) sociocultural theory, interactive learning environments

support students' zones of proximal development and facilitate language acquisition through meaningful interaction.

The need to develop medical case report writing skills was also emphasized. Analyzing real-life case reports and engaging in individual writing tasks can enhance both written communication and clinical reasoning. Students also expressed the necessity for curriculum content aligned with medical specialization exams (e.g., TUS, USMLE). Practice tests, specialized vocabulary lists, question analysis tasks, and timed exercises should be incorporated to familiarize students with exam formats and expectations.

With regard to the instructional process, students indicated a strong need for more experiential learning opportunities. The use of clinical case analyses, doctor-patient communication simulations, and role-play activities can increase engagement and support knowledge transfer. Furthermore, the diversification of instructional methods and consideration of individual learning differences are essential within a constructivist framework. To this end, methods such as problem-based learning, flipped classroom models, and game-based learning can be effectively employed to enhance instructional quality.

In terms of teaching materials, it was emphasized that the diversification of digital resources is necessary. Multimedia tools, augmented reality applications, interactive e-books, and infographics serve to increase retention and facilitate focus. It is also recommended that the effectiveness of these materials be evaluated through self-assessment tools and student feedback mechanisms.

Finally, the findings reveal a clear need for alternative assessment and evaluation methods beyond traditional exams. Tools such as self-assessments, peer evaluations, language portfolios, and reflective journals are effective in providing formative feedback. To evaluate clinical communication and academic writing more accurately, performance-based assessment tools should be employed. Additionally, the integration of technology-based platforms—such as Quizlet or AI-supported writing analysis tools—can support individual tracking and skill development. These findings reinforce the argument by Black and Wiliam (1998) that alternative assessment approaches are essential not only for measuring learning outcomes but also for evaluating the quality and depth of the learning process itself.

REFERENCES

- AlKanaan, H. (2022). Awareness regarding the implication of artificial intelligence in science education among pre-service science teachers. *International Journal of Instruction*, 15(3), 895-912. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2022.15348a>
- Black, P., & Wiliam, D. (1998). Assessment and Classroom Learning. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 5(1), 7–74. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0969595980050102>Büyüköztürk et al., 2019
- Chounta, I., Bardone, E., Raudsep, A., & Pedaste, M. (2021). Exploring teachers' perceptions of artificial intelligence as a tool to support their practice in estonian k-12 education. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education*, 32(3), 725-755. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40593-021-00243-5>
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publications.
- Dewey, J. (1938). *Experience and education*. New York: Macmillan Company.
- Elbawab, M., Henriques, R. (2023). Machine Learning applied to student attentiveness detection: Using emotional and non-emotional measures. *Education and Information Technologies* 28, 15717-15737. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-11814-5>
- Gay, L. R., Mills, G. E. and Airasian, P. (2009). *Education research competencies for analysis and applications*. Pearson, Columbus.
- Harden, R. M. (2001). AMEE Guide No. 21: Curriculum mapping: a tool for transparent and authentic teaching and learning. *Medical Teacher*, 23(2), 123–137. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01421590120036547>
- Harry, A. (2023). Transforming Patient Care: The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare; A mini Review. *BULLET: Jurnal Multidisiplin Ilmu*, 2, 530-533.
- Hinojo-Lucena, F., Díaz, I., Cáceres-Reche, M., & Rodríguez, J. (2019). Artificial intelligence in higher education: a bibliometric study on its impact in the scientific literature. *Education Sciences*, 9(1), 51. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci9010051>

- Huh, S. (2023). Are ChatGPT's knowledge and interpretation ability comparable to those of medical students in Korea for taking a parasitology examination?: a descriptive study. *Journal of Educational Evaluation for Health Professions*, 20(1). Doi: 10.3352/jeehp.2023.20.1.
- Johnson, R. B. and Christensen, L. B. (2008). *Educational research: quantitative, qualitative, and mixed approaches* (3rd ed.). Sage Publications, Inc., Los Angeles.
- Krueger, R. A. & Casey, M. A. (2015). *Focus groups: a practical guide for applied research* (5th ed.). Sage Publishing.
- Marino, M. T., Vasquez, E., Dieker, L., Basham, J., & Blackorby, J. (2023). The Future of Artificial Intelligence in Special Education Technology. *Journal of Special Education Technology*, 38(3), 404-416. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01626434231165977>
- Merriam, B. S. (2009). *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation*. San Francisco: Jossey Bass.
- Popenici, S. and Kerr, S. (2017). Exploring the impact of artificial intelligence on teaching and learning in higher education. *Research and Practice in Technology Enhanced Learning*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41039-017-0062-8>
- Richards, J. C. (2001). *Curriculum development in language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511667220>
- Saldaña, J. (2019). *The coding manual for qualitative research*. Londra: Sage.
- Strauss, A. L. & Corbin, J. M. (1990). *Basics of qualitative research*. New Bury Park: Sage.
- Stufflebeam, D. L., McCormick, C. H., Brinkerhoff, R. O., & Nelson, C. O. (1985). *Conducting educational need assessment*. Kluwer-Nijhoff Publishing.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: the development of higher psychological processes*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Yu, L., & Yu, Z. (2023). Qualitative and quantitative analyses of artificial intelligence ethics in education using VOSviewer and CiteNetExplorer. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1173262. Doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1173262
- Zhao, Q., & Nazir, S. (2022). English multimode production and usage by artificial intelligence and online reading for sustaining effectiveness. *Mobile Information Systems*, 2022(1), 678-682.